

THE METHODOLOGY OF TRAINING THE DATABASE AND THE TECHNIQUE OF EVALUATION USING IT.

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Annotation: This article describes the assessment of the professional competence of future informatics and information technology teachers in the continuous education system for creating a database, the requirements for them, the types of control and their organization. Innovative methods and means of strengthening knowledge, criteria for evaluating professional competence were analyzed and their effectiveness was studied.

Key words: Database, professional competence, assessment criteria, types of control, knowledge strengthening, innovative approach, test forms, educational nature of control.

Today, using the achievements of science and innovation activities in the continuous education system, consistent and stable development of all spheres of society and state life is becoming an important factor in building a worthy future of the country. The developed countries of the world, such as South Korea, England, Russia and Japan, have high professional competence, and the training of competitive personnel is considered as the main direction of development. In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority tasks of "further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the opportunities for quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" are defined, and in this regard, education aimed at the formation of professional competence improvement of the pedagogical system of forming the environment is of great importance. In the continuing education system, the training of specialized subjects and the assessment of the knowledge and skills of students in these subjects play an important role in the formation of professional competence of future informatics and information technology teachers in creating a database. This sometimes creates the problem of choosing the right tools and methods to properly organize the process and increase students' interest in science. The criteria for evaluating the knowledge, skills and qualifications of learners has always been a controversial topic. Because it is covered differently in different literature. However, the existing views can be summarized and it can be said that the criteria for evaluating the knowledge, skills and qualifications of learners are determined based on the goals and tasks of each subject, as well as the mastery level of learners in the group. If the teacher organizes control and accounting correctly, the effectiveness of the educational process increases. For this purpose, the Teacher must determine the level of mastery of the educational materials of the student. Supervision means the process of determining, measuring and evaluating the level of knowledge, skills and competences of the learner. detection and measurement is also called verification. Inspection is a component of control, and its main didactic task is to provide feedback between the teacher and students, to obtain objective information about the mastering of educational material by the pedagogue, and to ensure timely identification of knowledge deficiencies and

defects. The purpose of the examination is not only to determine the level and quality of the student's knowledge, but also the amount of his educational work. The use of electronic means of testing knowledge in teaching the database serves to increase the level of students' creative thinking and knowledge acquisition. There are modern programs that create such electronic tools, for example Ispring, MyTest programs. The advantage of mixed tasks over single tasks is that if a large number of tasks of the same type are performed, boredom or burnout can occur.

Mixed tasks develop skills such as being ready for different tasks each time, thinking creatively, and being ready for different situations. Good aspects of oral supervision and evaluation: - the professor-teacher has direct, live contact and communication with the student; - there is an opportunity to ask additional questions to determine the student's knowledge in depth; - oral response encourages the student to practice oral speech and active thinking; - a well-prepared student in verbal thinking can demonstrate his knowledge and additional learning; - during direct questioning, some doubts of the teacher about the student's learning will be eliminated. Advantages of written assessment: - the written answer is a documentary proof that the student has mastered the learning material; - is a practice for the student to express his thoughts on paper. One of the biggest disadvantages of the oral and written evaluation system is that the assessment of the student's knowledge is more subjective. Grades are often compared to other students, which can be downgraded or over graded. Advantages of test tools: - a well-designed and constructed test can accurately measure the quality and level of a student's knowledge acquisition, serve as an objective assessment; - the test can fully cover the main content of the subject. Test tools also have their own disadvantages, which are as follows: testing and evaluating knowledge with the help of a test does not allow the development of the student by sharply limiting his oral speech and writing. By marking the answers randomly, they may not answer the questions accurately. Prevention and elimination of such deficiencies is one of the main requirements for quality education. The control tasks prepared on the basis of questions and tasks that can interest the student will serve to form their future professional competence based on the acquired knowledge, not only in the subject, but also in increasing their interest in science.

Database and Database Management System (DBMS).

A data warehouse is an information model that stores and processes ordered data. In simpler terms, a model that stores the same type of information and presents it through the given queries. For example, a bookshelf is a data warehouse, i.e. it stores objects of the same type (books), or else a book of telephone numbers, where data of the same type, such as name, phone number is stored, which is also a data warehouse.

A database management system is a database creation, data processing and retrieval system. In short, MOBT does all the processes. The database only stores the data, MOBT does all the rest.

The data in the database is managed using SQL query languages, in which a query is sent to the MOBT, which is processed there, and it references the database to get the result, from there to the query retrieves the appropriate information and responds to the query:

Make a request:

SQL query -> MOBT -> Datastore

get result:

Data Warehouse -> MOBT — > Query Response

The following programs are examples of MBBT:

- Oracle;
- MySQL;
- Microsoft Office Access;
- MariaDB;
- Microsoft SQL Server;

The bottom line is that these programs you are thinking of are MOBTs, not data stores.

The database is part of MOBT, so when using these programs, it is correct to say "I have selected Oracle as my database management system" rather than "I have selected Oracle as my database management system".

Conclusion: Based on the points analyzed above, the use of a set of differentiated and non-standard tasks in evaluating competence is highly effective. In conclusion, it can be said that the process of covering each subject and subject is focused on the formation of high-level knowledge and professional competence of students, which will help them to become high-potential and competitive personnel in the future. First of all, it serves as the main factor for the development of society. After all, the training of highly qualified pedagogues, first of all, ensures the development of potential young people in the future.

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